

Relation between Blood in Urine and Perfume Allergy

Mah Rukh*, Aqsa Naeem, Syed Bilal Hussain & Muhammad Imran Qadir

Institute of Molecular Biology & Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.
Correspondence to (Mah Rukh) - mahrukhmahboob21@gmail.com*

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ABSTRACT

Some people love fragrance as it makes them feel good. They are more likely to use perfumes on daily basis regardless of their mild allergies to scents. This study relates the relation between blood in urine and perfume allergy. Hematuria is a condition in which blood releases from body with urine. When we see blood in our urine this condition is called gross hematuria and when we can't see the blood in urine with our naked eye it is known as microscopic hematuria. The other risk factors are age, infection and family history. Main symptoms of this disease are nausea, vomiting, fever, chills and pain in abdomen or back. Patients of hematuria often have normal renal function. Perfume allergy is caused by different chemicals which cause diseases in specific host. Perfumes have certain chemicals that can even penetrate our delicate skin. These chemicals then provoke our immune system and a storm of such response results in what we call as allergy. Headache, sneezing is a common symptom in this disease. 60% males have blood in urine and have perfume allergy while 53.75% females have blood in urine and have perfume allergy.

Keywords: Blood in urine, Perfume allergy, Gross hematuria, Microscopic hematuria, Chemicals.

1. Introduction

Hematuria is a condition in which blood releases from body with urine. It can be either visible or not with naked eye. When we see visible blood in our urine this condition is called gross hematuria and when we can't see the blood in urine with our naked eye it is known as microscopic hematuria. The main causes of blood urine are infection in urinary track, infection in kidney, stone in bladder or kidney, cancer and excess working. There are other risk factors as well including age, infection, family history. Main symptoms of this disease are nausea, vomiting, fever, chill and pain in abdomen or back. To avoid these kinds of diseases we have to drink excess water and take less salts, apply good hygiene habits and to prevent bladder cancer avoid smoking and stay away from chemicals. We can easily test for hematuria by blood test, CT scan and kidney biopsy.

Perfume allergy is caused by different chemicals which cause diseases in specific host. It is very difficult to find out the all ingredients present in perfume because it is a top secret and is only disclosed legally by the government of such country. Allergic contact dermatitis is a type of skin/perfume allergy which is caused when person is directly in contact with this chemical. It is also called irritant contact dermatitis [1-3]. If you feel headache, sneezing and some breathing problem then you are a part of 30% persons in the world who have perfume allergy. For successful treatment, it is necessary to detect the symptoms and avoid the products that cause this allergy.

2. Materials and Methods

100 contributors of Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan participated in this process.

Hematuria

If you note that your urine sample contains blood then you have to check hematuria by CT scan and MRI. Cystoscopy is another method in which tiny camera is attached with a thread and passed to the bladder to examine the infection in urethra.

Objective of the Study

This forecast explains link between hematuria and perfume allergy.

3. Result and Discussion

In this study total 20% males have blood in urine and it shows perfume allergy. 60% males have no blood in urine and shows perfume allergy. 0% males have blood in urine and they don't show perfume allergy. 20% males have no blood in urine and don't shows perfume allergy. Total 8% females have blood in urine and they show perfume allergy. 53.75% females have no blood in urine and show perfume allergy. 4.25% females have blood in urine and they don't show perfume allergy. 34% females have no blood in urine and don't shows perfume allergy [4-6].

Questionnaire based studies is very important as it helps to generate reliable results. It allows the participation of people from different areas and ethnicity thus, providing more reliable results.

Table 1. Link between hematuria and perfume allergy

Gender	Perfume Allergy		Don't have perfume allergy	
	Blood in urine	No blood in urine	Blood in urine	No blood in urine
Male	20%	60%	0%	20%
Female	8%	53.75%	4.25%	34%

4. Conclusion

20% males have blood in urine and have perfume allergy while 8% females have blood in urine and have perfume allergy.

Declarations

Source of Funding

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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